

The Beautiful System

Numbers and Symbols are interchangeably units, values, or lengths in metres, as appropriate. $\approx$ is “engineering equals” as opposed to mathematical equals =. So $3.14159265\dots \approx 3.1416$.

$$\pi \approx 3.1416$$

$$\varphi \approx 1.618$$

$$\varphi^2 = \varphi + 1 = 2.618$$

$$e \approx 2.7183$$

$$\acute{e} = e - 1 = 1.7183$$

$$m = \text{metre} = 1.000$$

$$\mathbb{C} = \text{royal cubit} = \pi/6 = 0.5236$$

$$f = \text{foot} = \mathbb{C}/\acute{e} = 0.5236/1.7183 \approx 0.30472$$

$$Y = \text{“megalithic yard”} = \mathbb{C} + f = 0.5236 + 0.30472 = 0.82832$$

$$M = \text{Grand Metre} = m + \mathbb{C} = 1.5236 \approx 5 \text{ feet}$$

$$S = \text{six feet (fathom)} = m + \mathbb{C} + f = 1.82832$$

$$\frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \pi - \varphi^2 = \mathbb{C} \quad m = \pi - \varphi - \mathbb{C} \approx \frac{7\pi}{5\varphi e}$$

$$\frac{\pi+1}{e} \approx \frac{\varphi^2}{\acute{e}} \left(= \frac{\varphi+1}{e-1} \right) \approx \pi - \varphi = \mathbb{C} + m = M$$

$$\text{digit} = \frac{52.36}{28} = 1.87 \text{ cm} \approx \frac{\pi\varphi}{e}$$

$$\frac{\mathbb{C}}{f} \approx \frac{e\mathbb{C}}{Y} \approx \frac{\acute{e}}{m} \approx \frac{\varphi^2}{M} \approx \frac{\pi}{S} \approx \acute{e} = 1.7183$$

This links the three key irrationals: π , φ , and e ,

with three base units of length: **foot**, (royal) **cubit**, and **metre**,

and three derived lengths: “**megalithic yard**”, **five feet** (grand metre), and **six feet**,

via a consistent ratio of $\acute{e}$.